

HIGHER EDUCATION REFORMS: UPDATE, DEVELOPMENT, UPGRADE

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Annotation: This article analyzes issues such as reforms, renewal, and quality improvement of the higher education system in Uzbekistan.

Key words: higher education, reform, private higher education, development, foreign experience, admission quota, competition, modern methods of teaching, spiritual and educational work.

In our country today, wide opportunities and conditions are being created for young people. Uzbekistan is gaining its own place and position in terms of integration into the world community, ensuring the rights of citizens, raising the reform of the education system to a new level.

In a series of speeches and speeches of the head of our state, in his speeches at the 72nd and 75th sessions of the UN General Assembly, opinions were expressed about the fact that suitable conditions are being created for young people, Uzbekistan is becoming a country of wide opportunities.

If we consider the education system alone, large-scale reforms in all parts of the education system have been implemented since the first years of independence, and in the following years, changes and updates in this regard have risen to a higher level.

In terms of reforming the higher education system, raising the quality level, it is worth emphasizing the work of applying foreign experience and creating competitive personnel. Significant results were also achieved in the reform of the post-secondary education system.

Today, our young people and researchers are not going through long and laborious processes, but in higher education institutions of each region, Specialized Scientific Councils have been established, and our young people are successfully defending selected scientific research works in their chosen fields and specializations.

If we see this in numbers, according to the information service of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, over the past 6 years, the number of higher educational institutions has increased from 77 to 170, and admission to them has increased by 3.5 times.

By supporting competition in higher education and attracting the private sector, 24 foreign and 27 non-state universities were established.

On this basis, the level of coverage of youth with higher education was increased from 9 percent to 32 percent.

In order to increase the level of coverage of higher education, the number of admissions to higher education institutions of the republic in the 2022-2023 academic year totaled 197 thousand 858. Including 16 thousand 933 is the admission rate for the master's degree. It has increased by 15% (27 thousand 203 people) compared to the previous academic year. In 2022, 25 new universities will be established, including 27 non-state higher educational institutions, 31 foreign universities, and 112 state universities. It is no secret that these numbers and indicators are constantly increasing.

Separate Pedagogical Institutes were established on the basis of 5 Pedagogical Institutes and 3 Pedagogical Faculties within the universities, Nukus and Termiz branches of Tashkent State Agrarian University and Termiz Branch of Tashkent State Technical University.

Taking into account the need for teachers in our country, Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages and Namangan State Institute of Foreign Languages were established.

Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers" and its Bukhara and Karshi branches were granted the status of a separate institute.

The Institute of Agrobiotechnologies, the Institute of Engineering and the Urgut branch were established at Samarkand State University. Also, the establishment of "New Uzbekistan" University is a special opportunity created for our talented youth.

At the same time, branches of leading foreign universities were established in our country. The branches of St. Petersburg State University, Russian National Research Medical University named after Pirogov, Kazan Federal University, Pisa University of Italy should be mentioned separately. The activities of foreign universities with such potential have a positive effect on the development of local universities.

The higher education process was completely transferred to the credit-module system. European ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System) system was adopted as the basis.

"Higher Education Management Information Systems" (HEMIS - Higher Education Management Information Systems) was developed as part of the "Digital University" project in order to drastically reduce the number of various reports and data received from higher education institutions on the educational process, to abandon the paper form of their preparation, and to digitize the management system. . This system includes "Administrative", "Educational", "Scientific" and "Financial" process management modules.

Starting from September 1, 2021, the group journal, class schedule, exam schedules, student rating book, learning records, attendance reports, diplomas and academic references were digitized in the "Educational Process" module by gradually introducing it in higher education institutions.

In the "Administrative process" module, the structure of the higher education institution, the student contingent and their movement, the management of information on the staff of professors and teachers, and the preparation of reports were digitized.

Supplying higher education institutions of the republic with educational literature is one of the priority directions of the education policy. In the last 5 years, 11 thousand 990 titles of new generation educational literature were created and published. In particular, as of

July 1 of this year, 1,527 titles (including 504 textbooks, 1,023 training manuals) of educational literature were allowed to be published.

In 2017-2022, in order to further improve the quality and efficiency of education in higher education institutions, 6 thousand 279 foreign experts were involved in the educational process, of which 1 thousand 845 are professors from Europe, 462 from America, 1 thousand 759 from Asia, 2 thousand 213 from CIS countries. - are teachers and experts in the field.

In the higher education system, great attention is being paid to improving scientific activity and capacity building. Today, 33,063 professors teach about 800,000 students at the Higher Education Institution. There are 13 thousand 2 people with scientific degrees, of which 2 thousand 687 have a doctor of science (DSc), 10 thousand 315 have a doctor of philosophy (PhD).

The rate of doctoral dissertation defense increased by 5.1 times compared to 2017, and the percentage of pedagogues with a scientific degree reached 39.3% in the country. In 2022, the number of quotas was increased by almost 100%, and 1993 quotas for doctoral studies (1704 PhDs, 128 DSc, 156 PhDs for targeted doctoral studies, 5 DSc) and 308 quotas for intern-research were allocated to universities of the ministry system. Today, 5 thousand 166 doctoral students and 379 interns-researchers are engaged in research activities in higher education institutions.

Currently, 71 higher educational institutions and 88 scientific organizations (159 in total) have established doctoral programs. Research supervisors/consultants were allowed to supervise up to 5 researchers. In 2021, 1,765 dissertations were defended, including 244 Doctor of Science (DSc), 1,521 Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degrees. In the first half of 2022, 929 dissertations were defended in higher educational institutions of the republic.

Speaking about the conditions and opportunities created in the higher education system, it is necessary to pay special attention to the International Innovation University located in the city of Karshi, Kashkadarya region. The university has 8 educational areas, and trainings are organized in modern, comfortable and bright rooms, using interactive methods.

At the university, special attention is paid to meaningful spending of free time of students. An information resource center equipped with electronic and educational literature and computer classes also serves to improve students' knowledge and skills.

The youth of the "Zakovat" intellectual club of Oliyohoh have been winning a number of prize-winning results. The activity of circles in the fields of science has also been established, and it should be noted that the systematic mechanisms of working with qualified professors and students have been created.

So, today in our country, all conditions and opportunities are being created for the youth and the future generation. In the words of the President, healthy competition, exchange of experience, and large-scale cooperation between state universities and private universities are planned. Of course, these changes will give their results.

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